

SENSORY QUALITIES OF COTTON FRUIT *Sandoricum koetjape* PULP KETCHUP

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ABSTRACT

Cotton fruit (*Sandoricum koetjape*) is a tropical fruit native to Southeast Asia, including the Philippines, and is commonly available in local markets during its peak season. Traditionally consumed fresh, its pulp also shows potential as a base ingredient for condiments such as ketchup. This study aimed to determine the sensory qualities and level of acceptability of cotton fruit pulp ketchup blended with basic ingredients, specifically sugar syrup and chili powder. An experimental research design was employed using three treatments: T1 – Original Blend, T2 – Sweet Blend, and T3 – Spicy Blend. Sensory evaluation was conducted using descriptive tests and level of liking assessments in terms of appearance, aroma, taste, and texture. Results showed that Treatments 1 and 3 obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.06 for appearance, described as moderately appealing. In terms of aroma, Treatment 3 received the highest weighted mean of 3.10, indicating a moderately pleasant aroma. Treatment 3 also dominated in taste with a weighted mean of 3.22, described as moderately spicy, and in texture with a weighted mean of 2.64, interpreted as moderately refined. Overall acceptability results revealed that the spicy blend (Treatment 3) achieved the highest average weighted mean of 2.96, corresponding to “like moderately.” The findings indicate that cotton fruit pulp ketchup, particularly the spicy blend, is generally acceptable to consumers in terms of sensory attributes. Based on these positive results, the patronage and consumption of spicy cotton fruit pulp ketchup is recommended as an alternative condiment and as an ingredient in various culinary applications.

Keywords: *Sensory qualities, Cotton fruit, Ketchup, Innovation, Consumer acceptability*

INTRODUCTION

Innovation is a new trend entailed by industrial revolution which provides access and opportunity to create new. Among the various innovated product is food condiment such as ketchup. Ketchup is one of the most refined condiment from its history which complements food with a tangy, sweet blend, and spicy taste. The advent in cooking has brought a lot of changes in the society, more so in the hospitality industry. Innovative cooking has been a powerful tool of a food outlet to gleam from among the ordinary choices.

The most common available in the Philippine market are Tomato Ketchup, Banana Ketchup, Mushroom Ketchup, and Mango Ketchup. Jasmin Wiggins of National Geographic once published an article on April 21, 2014 entitled "How was ketchup invented?" which states that, in United Kingdom, Mushroom Ketchup has been originally produced and eventually distributed to United States of America wherein Tomato Ketchup was originated in replacement of the latter as America's innovation.

Furthermore, there has been no documented study or research work of Cotton Fruit made as ketchup internationally and locally. In addition, the researcher found the sensory qualities of Cotton Fruit Pulp acceptable to made as ketchup. Naturally, pulp of the said fruit was only neglected due to lack of ideas on how consume it other than eating it raw. Cotton fruit also contains valuable nutrients which are essential to the body primarily iron, calcium, phosphorus, protein, fats, carbohydrates and fiber.

According to Kotler (1991), "an innovation refers to any good, service, or idea that is perceived by someone as new. The idea may have a long history, but it is an innovation to the person who sees it as new." Further, the study was anchored on the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) Theory developed by E. M. Rogers in 1962, wherein the adoption of a new idea, behavior, or product (i.e., "innovation") does not occur simultaneously in a social system; rather, it is a process in which some individuals are more likely to adopt an innovation earlier than others. Previous studies have shown that early adopters possess different characteristics compared with later adopters.

In connection with this, prolific business management author, professor, and corporate consultant Peter Drucker (1985) advanced the Opportunity-Based Theory, which explained the principle behind Rebecca Tubongbanua of Guimaras in innovating Mango Ketchup. Drucker contended that entrepreneurs excel at recognizing and exploiting opportunities created by social, technological, and cultural changes.

The researcher exercised caution in conducting the study because some product innovations have been pursued without adequate research to determine what target customers truly want. The dissonance between what exists and what is expected, or what is assumed by the public, can lead organizations to failure but can also serve as a source of inspiration for innovation. Customer reviews, feedback, and complaints were identified as effective means of determining such incongruities. Over the years, significant changes have occurred in how people perceive the world. Perceptions have changed rapidly due to technological advancement and the influence of social networks, allowing consumers

to alter their views of a product, brand, or industry almost overnight. These shifts in perception have opened opportunities for businesses to innovate and develop products aligned with evolving customer perspectives (Drucker, 1985). When promoting an innovation to a target population, understanding the characteristics that facilitate or hinder adoption was deemed essential (LaMorte, 2019).

The Theory of Food Choice Development stated that food choice in humans, like other omnivores, was predominantly learned behavior. Very few aversions were innate, and even these could be modified through learning. Learning began before birth and continued throughout life, ranging from unconscious conditioning and imitation to cognitive learning. As a result, food choice was identified as a dynamic behavior subject to continuous change and influence across different levels. Preferences for staple foods tended to remain relatively stable within cultures, although globalization and travel have increased variability. Preferences for other foods and condiments varied widely among individuals and across different life stages and eating situations (Köster et al., 2006).

This research and innovation of a local product were supported by the 1987 Philippine Constitution, Article XIV, Section 10, which emphasized the importance of science and technology in national development and innovation.

The researcher's emphasis on consumer health as an outcome of Cotton Fruit Pulp Ketchup was anchored on existing legal frameworks, particularly Republic Act No. 10611, otherwise known as the Food Safety Act of 2013.

Product competitiveness and market-responsive design were mandated under Republic Act No. 10557, which declared the State's policy of enhancing innovation, sustainability, and design-driven competitiveness.

In recent years, the Philippine government has actively promoted the cultivation and innovation of farm products. The Department of Tourism supported this initiative through Republic Act No. 10816, or the Farm Tourism Development Act of 2016, which encouraged the utilization of local agricultural products through innovative processing acceptable to both local and international markets.

Farm tourism was defined as the practice of attracting visitors to agricultural areas for production, educational, and recreational purposes, highlighting agriculture's role in food security and livelihood generation (RA 10816).

In relation to food technology innovation, National Geographic's *Future of Food* series reported that ketchup had become a staple condiment in American households. Historical accounts traced its origins to Southeast Asia, with early British adaptations appearing in the 18th century (Wiggins, 2014).

Over time, tomato ketchup emerged as the dominant variant. It was characterized as a sweet and tangy sauce made primarily from tomatoes, sugar, vinegar, and spices. Heinz was identified as the market leader in both the United States and the United Kingdom, followed by Hunt's in the U.S. market.

Tomato ketchup was commonly used as a condiment for fried and greasy foods and served as a base ingredient for other sauces. Its versatility contributed to its growing

demand in emerging regions, particularly Southeast Asia, where local cuisines integrated ketchup into street food and home cooking (Bhisey, 2016).

Despite its popularity, the rise of alternative condiments such as mustard and barbecue sauce posed competition in the market, prompting manufacturers to diversify product lines.

In this study, the researcher sought to innovate ketchup using Cotton Fruit Pulp, which was considered potentially marketable due to its nutritional value and local availability. Santol (*Sandoricum koetjape*), a tropical fruit native to Southeast Asia, was selected as the primary ingredient. The yellow variety was chosen due to its desirable acidity and flavor profile when ripe.

Santol pulp was found to contain essential nutrients such as iron, fiber, calcium, phosphorus, and B vitamins (Herben, 2020). These attributes supported its potential as a functional ingredient for ketchup production.

The Cotton Fruit Pulp Ketchup emphasized iron content, a nutrient typically absent in commercial ketchup. Iron deficiency had been identified as a global health concern, particularly among children and women (WHO, 2007; Bjarnadottir, 2019).

Related studies on santol-based products, such as santol vinegar, demonstrated the fruit's versatility and health benefits (Coleman, 2012). Fruits were recognized as essential dietary components, and innovative processing methods increased their accessibility and consumption (Arenas et al., 2016).

Ultimately, the study aimed to develop an alternative ketchup made from Cotton Fruit Pulp, which was confirmed to be rich in iron, fiber, carbohydrates, phosphorus, and vitamins essential to human health and was readily available in local communities.

Research Questions

Specifically, the study was conducted to determine the potential of utilizing Cotton Fruit *Sandoricum koetjape* Pulp as Ketchup in three identified treatments: Original Blend, Sweet Blend and Spicy as condiments used by gastronomes in Bohol. It also aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the product description of Cotton Fruit *Sandoricum koetjape* Pulp Ketchup in terms of ingredients and costs, tools and equipment, procedures and shelf-life?
2. What are the sensory characteristics and the level of Cotton Fruit *Sandoricum koetjape* Pulp Ketchup in terms of appearance, aroma, taste and texture?
3. Is there a significant difference on the level of likeness of Cotton Fruit *Sandoricum koetjape* Pulp Ketchup among the three treatments?
4. What recommendation could be proposed based on the result of the study?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed experimental research using completely randomized design in choosing the identified respondents to assess the three treatments. These treatments were examined and criteria were set as bases for comparison. Descriptive research design was also used to determine the quality characteristics and level of likeness of Cotton Fruit Pulp Ketchup in terms of appearance, aroma, taste, and texture of the three different treatments. The respondents were categorized according to their expertise and work experiences however, they used the same questionnaire and rating sheet.

The researcher used the modified 4-Point Hedonic Scale of Gatchalian to determine the sensory characteristics and level of likeness of Cotton Fruit Pulp Ketchup. The following scale was observed: four (4)-like very much which refers to extreme satisfaction of the product, three (3)- like moderately, an average satisfaction of the product, two (2)-like slightly which describes the minimal satisfaction of the product, while one (1)- dislike refers to the total dissatisfaction. A relevant questionnaire was also distributed that served as rating sheet for sample testing. On the questionnaire, treatments were represented with codes to avoid pre-judgement and rating scale for sensory characteristics and overall likeness was also provided.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Table 1
Running cost and the selling price of the Cotton Fruit *Sandoricum koetjape* Pulp Ketchup

Qty.	Unit	Ingredients	Three Treatments			Unit Cost	Total Cost
			T1	T2	T3		
1 1/2	kg	Cotton Fruit	/	/	/	60.00/kg	₱90.00
800	ml	Water	/	/	/	1.00/800ml	1.00
30	ml	White Vinegar	/	/	/	6.00/200ml	0.90
10	g	Rock Salt	/	/	/	5.00/400g	0.13
3	g	White Pepper Powder	/	/	/	5.00/3g	5.00
1.5	g	Garlic Powder	/	/	/	5.00/3g	2.50
1.5	g	Onion Powder	/	/	/	5.00/3g	2.50
400	ml	Sugar Syrup	/		/	22.00/800ml	11.00
500	ml	Sugar Syrup		/		22.00/800ml	13.75
1.5	g	Chili Powder			/	5.00/3g	2.50
Running Cost			Treatment 1		Treatment 2		Treatment 3
Total Cost of Ingredients			₱113.03		₱115.78		₱115.53
Labor Cost 10%			11.30		11.58		11.55
Operational Cost 15%			16.95		17.37		17.33
Mark-Up 20%			22.61		23.16		23.11
Running Cost			₱163.89		₱167.87		₱167.51
Yield (1400ml)			7 Bottles		7 Bottles		7 Bottles
Selling Price per bottle @ 200ml			₱23.41 or ₱23.00		₱23.98 or ₱24.00		₱23.93 or ₱24.00

Table 1 shows the running cost and the selling price of the Cotton Fruit Pulp Ketchup. The three treatments were subjected to the same percentage of additional costs. Labor Cost of 10%, Operational Cost of 15%, and Mark-up of 20% and all treatments have yielded the same volume. Each variety yielded 1400ml, however, the selling volume of the finished product was 200ml per bottle. To this effect, since they have the same additional percentage cost and yield, the prices have directly increased proportionally making the Treatment 1 at Php 23. 41 as the lowest price, Treatment 2 at Php 23.98 as the highest price, and Treatment 3 at Php 23.93.

Table 2
Tools, materials and equipment in the preparation of Cotton Fruit *Sandoricum koetjape* Pulp Ketchup

Items	Quantity	Unit
Tools and Equipment		
Kitchen Knife	1	pc
Chopping Board	1	pc
Measuring Cup	1	set
Measuring Spoon	1	set
Ceramic Bowls	1	pc
Non-stick Casserole	1	pc
Wooden Ladle	1	pc
Tablespoon	1	pc
Teaspoon	1	pc
Funnel	1	pc
Food Weighing Scale	1	unit
Turbo Blender	1	unit

Table 2 presents the tools, materials, and equipment used in the preparation of Cotton Fruit (*Sandoricum koetjape*) Pulp Ketchup. These include basic kitchen implements such as knives, chopping boards, measuring cups and spoons, ceramic bowls, and cooking utensils necessary for ingredient preparation, measurement, and mixing. A non-stick casserole and wooden ladle were utilized during the cooking process to ensure even heat distribution and to prevent the product from sticking or burning. The use of a food weighing scale and standardized measuring tools ensured accuracy and consistency in ingredient proportions across all treatments.

The turbo blender was essential in producing a smooth and uniform pulp, which directly influenced the texture of the finished ketchup, while a funnel was used to facilitate clean and efficient bottling. All tools, materials, and equipment employed in the study are commonly available in the local market, making the process practical and replicable for household or small-scale production. Prior to use, proper washing, rinsing, and sanitizing procedures were strictly observed to ensure food safety and to minimize the risk of contamination during the preparation of the product.

Table 3
Shelf life observation of Cotton Fruit *Sandoricum koetjape* Pulp Ketchup

Treatment	Days of Observation at room temperature		
	Day 1-19	Days 20-22	Days 23-25
T1	No Changes Occurred in the ketchup	White molds were observed	White molds started to increase and odor gets stronger than ordinary (Not safe for consumption)
T2	No Changes Occurred in the ketchup	White molds were observed	White molds started to increase and odor gets stronger than ordinary (Not safe for consumption)
T3	No Changes Occurred in the ketchup	White molds were observed	White molds started to increase and odor gets stronger than ordinary (Not safe for consumption)
Days of Observation in a Chiller			
T1	No Changes Occurred in the ketchup	White molds were observed	White molds started to increase and odor gets stronger than ordinary (Not safe for consumption)
T2	No Changes Occurred in the ketchup	White molds were observed	White molds started to increase and odor gets stronger than ordinary (Not safe for consumption)
T3	No Changes Occurred in the ketchup	White molds were observed	White molds started to increase and odor gets stronger than ordinary (Not safe for consumption)

As shown in Table 3, Cotton Fruit Pulp Ketchup was observed in varied places to get the shelf-life, in a chiller and in a room temperature. Both were observed daily until on the 20th day where white molds were observed. On the 23rd day, white molds increased and odor got stronger than the ordinary, and the Ketchup was then declared unsafe for consumption and finally it was disposed.

Table 4
Nutritional Analysis of Cotton Fruit *Sandoricum koetjape* Pulp Ketchup

Analysis	Test Method	Result
Carbohydrates, g/100g	By Computation	19.4
Fat, g/100g	Mojonnier Extraction	0.856

Crude Protein (N x 6.25), g/100g	Kjeldahl	0.694
Phosphorus, ppm	UV-VIS Spectrometry	82
Calcium, µg/g	Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry	116
Iron, µg/g	Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry	3.87
Crude Fiber, g/100g	ANKOM Fiber Analyzer	0.40
Crude Ash, g/100g	Ignition – Gravimetric	1.25
Moisture, g/100g	Vacuum Oven Drying	77.8

Table 4 presents the Nutritional Analysis of Cotton Fruit *Sandoricum koetjape* Pulp Ketchup particularly Treatment 3 (Spicy). The product contained 116 microgram of calcium and 3.87 microgram of iron. Calcium is needed for muscles to move and for nerves to carry messages between the brain and every body part. It helps blood vessels move blood throughout the body and to help release hormones and enzymes that affect almost every function in the human body.

The recommended daily intake for calcium is 1000g. On the other hand, body needs iron for growth and development which Cotton Fruit Ketchup has. The body uses iron to make hemoglobin, a protein in red blood cells that carries oxygen from the lungs to all parts of the body, and myoglobin, a protein that provides oxygen to muscles. The recommended iron intake for the body of an adult is 20-25 g. There is also phosphorus in the product in which it is recommended that healthy adults get between 800 mg and 1,200 mg of phosphorus each day.

It has less content of crude fiber or indigestible cellulose, pentosans and lignin which is only 0.40g, 1.25g of crude ash or incinerated residue, 0.694g of crude protein and 0.856g of Fat. Lastly, Cotton Fruit Pulp Ketchup contains 77.8g of moisture from the Cotton Fruit Pulp, sugar syrup and water.

Table 5
Sensory Qualities Evaluation of Cotton Fruit *Sandoricum koetjape* Pulp Ketchup

Sensory Attributes	Treatment 1		Treatment 2		Treatment 3	
	WM	Description	WM	Description	WM	Description
Appearance	3.06	Moderately Appealing	3.00	Moderately Appealing	3.06	Moderately Appealing
Aroma	2.88	Moderately Pleasant	3.02	Moderately Pleasant	3.10	Moderately Pleasant
Taste	2.74	Moderately Tangy	3.00	Moderately Sweet Blend	3.22	Moderately Spicy

Texture	2.32	Slightly Refined	2.40	Slightly Refined	2.64	Moderately Refined
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Table 5 shows the presentation and interpretation of the sensory qualities of Cotton Fruit *Sandoricum koetjape* Pulp Ketchup in terms of appearance, aroma, taste, and texture. For the Appearance, Treatment 1 the light orange in color and Treatment 3 Redish-Orange got the same weighted mean of 3.06 while Treatment 2 Red-Orange has a weighted mean of 3.00 all belonged and described as “moderately appealing”. The result expressed that the appearance of all treatments was moderately appealing. Food appearance is determined mostly by surface color as the first sensation that the consumer perceives and uses as a tool to either accept or reject food (Leon et al., 2006). For the aroma, Treatment 3 got the highest weighted mean of 3.10 followed by Treatment 2 of 3.02, and Treatment 1 that has 2.88 weighted mean. All treatments were described as moderately pleasant.

For the taste, Treatment 3 the spicy has the highest weighted mean of 3.22 followed by Treatment 2 the sweet blend of 3.00 weighted mean, and Treatment 1 the tangy taste that has 2.74 weighted mean. Still, the three treatments were described as moderately tasteful.

And for the texture, Treatment 3 got the highest weighted mean of 2.64 which is “moderately refined”. However, Treatment 2 got 2.40 and Treatment 1 got 2.32 weighted means that were described as slightly refined. Result showed that Treatment 3 was more refined than Treatments 1 and 2. Result for the texture expressed more improvement to reach refine texture. Overall, the identified sensory characteristics appearance, aroma, taste, and texture were the key indicators of Fruit *Sandoricum koetjape* Pulp which expressed acceptability as Ketchup. Perceiving these sensory characteristics in a particular food does not necessarily mean that an individual will or will not choose to consume that food. Rather it is the individual’s liking for that particular food which will be the determining factor (Shepherd, 1999).

Table 6
Overall Acceptability Level of Cotton Fruit *Sandoricum koetjape* Pulp Ketchup

Sensory Attributes	Treatment 1		Treatment 2		Treatment 3	
	WM	Description	WM	Description	WM	Description
Appearance	2.82	Like Moderately	3.02	Like Moderately	2.98	Like Moderately
Aroma	2.84	Like Moderately	2.96	Like Moderately	2.92	Like Moderately
Taste	2.56	Like Moderately	2.78	Like Moderately	3.14	Like Moderately
Texture	2.38	Like Slightly	2.42	Like Slightly	2.82	Like Moderately

Average Weighted Mean	2.65	Like Moderately	2.79	Like Moderately	2.96	Like Moderately
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Table 6 revealed that Treatment 2 has the highest level of likeness in terms of appearance which is 3.02 followed by Treatment 3 at 2.98 and Treatment 1 at 2.82. All treatments were described as liked moderately for its appearance. Treatment 2 got the highest weighted mean of 2.96 for the level of likeness in aroma. It was followed by Treatment 3 with 2.92, and Treatment 1 that has 2.84 weighted means.

All treatments, were liked moderately in its aroma. In terms of taste, Treatment 3 the Spicy Cotton Fruit Pulp Ketchup got the highest weighted mean of 3.14 that is described as “Like Moderately”. Its rating topped from among all ratings of the other sensory characteristics for the level of likeness. Treatment 2 has a weighted mean of 2.78, and Treatment 1 has 2.56 weighted mean. All treatments were liked moderately. And for the texture, Treatment 3 has the highest weighted mean of 2.82 described as “like moderately”, while Treatment 2 got 2.42 and Treatment 1 got 2.38 weighted means described as “like slightly”. The likeness level for texture expressed that all treatments were liked moderately.

Table 7
Significant Difference between the level of likeness in terms of the appearance, aroma, taste and texture of Cotton Fruit *Sandoricum koetjape* Pulp Ketchup

Source	SS	df	Level of Significance	F-value	p-value (Sig.)	Decision
Between-treatments	0.1869	2	0.05	1.9405	0.1992	Accept Ho
Within-treatments	0.4333	9				

Table 7 is the presentation of the significant difference wherein, there is no significant difference between the level of likeness in terms of the appearance, aroma, taste and texture of Cotton Fruit *Sandoricum koetjape* Pulp Ketchup in Scale B. This means that the three treatments of Cotton Fruit *Sandoricum koetjape* Pulp Ketchup were like moderately based on the overall level of likeness on descriptive and preference test.

Conclusions

The study confirmed the potential of cotton fruit (*Sandoricum koetjape*) pulp as a viable raw material for ketchup production, demonstrating its acceptability as an alternative condiment. Sensory evaluation results showed that all three treatments—Original, Sweet, and Spicy blends—were rated “like moderately” in terms of appearance, aroma, taste, and texture, with no significant difference among treatments. However, the Spicy Blend (Treatment 3) consistently obtained the highest weighted means, particularly in taste, texture, and overall acceptability, indicating a stronger consumer preference. The

inclusion of chili powder enhanced the sensory appeal of the product without substantially increasing production cost, making it competitive in pricing and yield.

Shelf-life evaluation revealed that the cotton fruit pulp ketchup remained safe for consumption for up to 19 days under both room temperature and chilled conditions, emphasizing the need for improved preservation techniques for extended storage. Nutritional analysis further showed that the product contains essential minerals such as calcium, iron, and phosphorus, contributing to its nutritional value. Overall, the findings establish that cotton fruit pulp ketchup is an acceptable, nutritious, and cost-efficient product that supports the utilization of indigenous fruits. With further improvements in processing, shelf life, and packaging, the product shows strong potential for household use and small-scale commercialization.

Recommendations

Based on the results and discussion of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Adopt Treatment 3 (Spicy) for potential commercialization, as it consistently obtained the highest weighted means in taste, texture, and overall acceptability, while maintaining a competitive selling price comparable to the other treatments.
2. Improve product shelf life through formulation and processing enhancements, such as adjusting acidity levels, improving sanitation practices, or exploring natural preservatives and proper packaging methods, since mold growth was observed starting on the 20th day under both room and chilled conditions.
3. Enhance texture refinement across all treatments, particularly Treatments 1 and 2, by optimizing blending, sieving, or cooking processes to achieve a more refined consistency that aligns with consumer preference reflected in Treatment
4. Conduct further nutritional and functional studies, including vitamin content, antioxidant properties, and comparative analysis with commercial ketchup, to strengthen the product's value proposition and support health-related marketing claims.
5. Undertake extended consumer testing and market feasibility studies, involving a larger and more diverse group of respondents, to validate acceptability results, assess willingness to pay, and determine the product's commercial potential in local and regional markets.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors hereby attest that all ethical guidelines were followed in the conduct of this study. All participants gave their informed consent before beginning the study, and they were informed of their freedom to leave at any time without facing any repercussions. All respondents' privacy was protected during the study, and their welfare was given first consideration. This study was conducted without any conflicts of interest. To maintain the integrity and uniqueness of the work, plagiarism was rigorously avoided. The study's

goals were achieved with academic rigor and ethical responsibility thanks to the objective interpretation of the results and their exclusive use for research.

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REFERENCES

- Arenas, M. C., Cruz, R. T., & Villanueva, M. E. (2016). Development of powdered santol (*Sandoricum koetjape*) juice drink. *Journal of Food Processing and Preservation*, 40(5), 1021–1028. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfpp.12673>
- BARDigest. (2012). Santol marmalade production and health benefits. Bureau of Agricultural Research. Retrieved from <https://www.bar.gov.ph/index.php/resources/bardigest>
- Bhisey, R. (2016). Global tomato ketchup market analysis. Market Research Future. Retrieved from <https://www.marketresearchfuture.com/reports/tomato-ketchup-market-1546>
- Bjarnadottir, A. (2019). Iron deficiency: Symptoms, causes, and treatment. Healthline. Retrieved from <https://www.healthline.com/nutrition/iron-deficiency-signs-symptoms>
- Coleman, E. (2012). Vinegar: Health benefits and uses. *Nutrition Today*, 47(4), 178–182. Retrieved from <https://journals.lww.com/nutritiontoday>
- Drucker, P. F. (1985). *Innovation and entrepreneurship: Practice and principles*. Harper & Row. Retrieved from <https://books.google.com/books?id=E0ZpQgAACAAJ>
- Herben, D. (2020). Nutritional profile of santol fruit. *Nutrition Data*. Retrieved from <https://nutritiondata.self.com>
- Köster, E. P., Mojet, J., Frewer, L., Trijp, H., & Postma, E. (2006). Theories of food choice development. *Food Quality and Preference*, 17(1–2), 1–13. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2005.04.001>
- Kotler, P. (1991). *Marketing management: Analysis, planning, implementation, and control* (7th ed.). Prentice Hall. Retrieved from <https://books.google.com/books?id=OT6uAAAAMAAJ>
- LaMorte, W. W. (2019). Diffusion of innovation theory. Boston University School of Public Health. Retrieved from <https://sphweb.bumc.bu.edu/otlt/mph-modules/sb/behavioralchangetheories>

- Leon, K., Mery, D., Pedreschi, F., & Leon, J. (2006). Color measurement in Lab* units from RGB digital images. *Food Research International*, 39(10), 1084–1091. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2006.03.006>
- Philippine Board of Investments. (2018). Industry profile: Food condiments and sauces. Retrieved from <https://boi.gov.ph/industry-profiles>
- Republic Act No. 10557, Philippine Design Competitiveness Act. (2013). Official Gazette of the Republic of the Philippines. Retrieved from <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2013/05/15/republic-act-no-10557>
- Republic Act No. 10611, Food Safety Act of 2013. (2013). Official Gazette of the Republic of the Philippines. Retrieved from <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2013/08/23/republic-act-no-10611>
- Republic Act No. 10816, Farm Tourism Development Act of 2016. (2016). Official Gazette of the Republic of the Philippines. Retrieved from <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2016/07/21/republic-act-no-10816>
- Rogers, E. M. (1962). *Diffusion of innovations*. Free Press. Retrieved from <https://books.google.com/books?id=9U1K5LjUOwEC>
- Shepherd, R. (1999). Factors influencing food preferences and choice. *Food Research International*, 32(9), 637–644. Retrieved from [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0963-9969\(99\)00057-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0963-9969(99)00057-1)
- Wiggins, J. (2014, April 21). A brief history of ketchup. *National Geographic*. Retrieved from <https://www.nationalgeographic.com/history/article/ketchup-history>
- World Health Organization. (2007). *Assessing the iron status of populations*. WHO Press. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241596107>